

Dispersion-diversity signal processing in Space-division multiplexing fibers

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ABSTRACT

Beyond high-capacity digital communications, space-division multiplexing fibers bring significant benefits to microwave signal distribution and processing, as not only space but also chromatic dispersion are introduced as new degrees of freedom. The key lies in developing new fibers where each individual core/mode is tailored to provide parallel dispersion-diversity signal processing.

1. I N T R O D U C T I O N

In recent years, there has been a surge of interest in space-division multiplexing (SDM) technologies, which has resulted in the emergence of innovative multicore (MCF) and few-mode (FMF) optical fibers, [1]. The development of these SDM fibers has been driven by the need for ultra-high-capacity communications that could take advantage of the space dimension [1]. By incorporating the chromatic dispersion dimension, both MCFs and FMFs can offer interesting benefits for optical and microwave signal processing, provided that each core/mode is customized to enable tunable sampled true-time delay line (TTDL) operation [2]. These dispersion-diversity SDM fibers can provide various functionalities, such as parallel interference-controlled signal distribution, chromatic dispersion compensation, time differentiation and integration, Fourier transformation, multi-gigabit-per-second analogue-to-digital conversion, and Talbot-based self-imaging phenomena, amongst others. One promising application of dispersion-diversity MCFs is in 5G and Beyond fiber-wireless communications, where they exhibit high potential for reconfigurable microwave signal processing [3] based on tunable true-time delay line operation. This includes signal filtering, radio beam-steering in phased array antennas, instantaneous frequency measurement, or arbitrary waveform generation, as shown in Fig. 1 for a generic dispersion-diversity SDM optical fiber (N cores/modes).

This paper presents a compilation of our latest experimental demonstrations showcasing these functionalities in dispersion-diversity multicore [4-8] and few-mode [10-12] fibers.

Figure 1. Tunable sampled TTDL implemented on a generic dispersion-diversity SDM fiber with application to: (a) microwave signal filtering, (b) radio beam-steering in phased array antennas, (c) pulse generation and shaping, and (d) microwave frequency measurement.

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One of the multicore fibers we have implemented consists of 7 trench-assisted step-index cores that differ in terms of radial dimensions and dopant concentration. In other words, the 7 cores were drawn from 7 different GeO₂-doped preforms. The cross section of the fiber is illustrated in Fig. 2 (a), where the core pitch is 40 μm and the cladding diameter is 150 μm . Fig. 2(b) shows the measured spectral differential group delay between pairs of cores (between the seventh core and the rest), where linear continuous tunability is achieved over a 30-nm optical wavelength range. Each core provides the necessary chromatic dispersion D , ranging from 13.9 to 20.3 ps/(km.nm) in approximately 1-ps/(km.nm) increments (ΔD), [5].

a) Fabricated 7-core fiber

b) Measured tunable TTDL performance

Figure 2. Dispersion-diversity MCF: (a) Photograph of the fiber's cross-section, (b) Measured spectral differential group delays between the 7th core and the rest.

2.1 Microwave signal filtering

We achieve microwave signal filtering by detecting together all the delayed signal samples at the output of the MCF. The Free Spectral Range (FSR) is inversely proportional to the differential group delay between samples $\Delta\tau$. To take advantage of space diversity, (which involves exploiting samples from different cores), we use cores 3 to 7 for 5-sample operation, as cores 1 and 2 do not satisfy the true-time delay line condition fully [5]. In Fig. 3 (a), the measured filter response is shown, with the blue dotted, orange dashed, yellow solid, purple dash-dotted, and green solid lines representing the optical wavelengths of 1540, 1545, 1550, 1555, and 1560 nm, respectively. Our approach enables continuous tunability, with FSR ranging from 20 GHz at 1540 nm down to 6.7 GHz at 1560 nm, without any significant degradation. Furthermore, if we utilize wavelength diversity, (which involves using samples provided by different wavelengths), all seven cores can be used. In this case, we achieve tunability by varying the optical wavelength separation and/or the core selection.

2.2 Optical beamforming in phased array antennas

The MCF-based true-time delay line can be utilized for optical beamforming in phased array antennas, provided that the output of each core is directed towards a specific radiating element of the antenna. We have successfully demonstrated tunable squint-free radio beam-steering in an 8-element in-house-fabricated antenna operating at a radiofrequency of 26 GHz, using space diversity [6]. In an anechoic chamber, we measured the radiation pattern at various optical wavelengths, ranging from 1542.50 to 1548.28 nm in increments of 0.96 nm. Fig. 3 (b) displays the measured radiation pattern, where the beam-pointing angle steers approximately from -40° to 43° .

2.3 Broadband microwave frequency measurement

We have introduced and experimentally validated as well a tunable microwave frequency measurement technique that incorporates multiple amplitude comparison functions in the MCF, enabling high-resolution retrieval of unknown radiofrequencies over a wide bandwidth [7]. Each comparison function is determined by the ratio of frequency responses from two distinct microwave filters that are constructed with two different fiber cores. Our approach offers advantages over prior methods, such as reducing the need for modulators and photodetectors, while increasing compactness. Fig. 3 (c) illustrates the estimated microwave frequency versus the input frequency (blue) and the residual measurement error (red) for five different sets of measurements. We achieved a residual error of ± 71 MHz within a measurement range of 0.5-40 GHz.

2.4 Arbitrary waveform generation

We have successfully showcased the generation of arbitrary waveforms for a range of ultra-wideband pulses [8]. In this case, after propagating through the MCF, the complimentary branches of a balanced photodetector supply the necessary positive and negative signal pulses that will assemble the required waveform. We produced various waveforms, from monocycles consisting of two samples to seven-sample combinations, by applying incoherent filtering to a baseband 12.5-Gb/s input bit-rate pulse. As an illustration, Fig. 3 (d) illustrates the tunability of the measured temporal waveforms for a quadruplet signal (consisting of five samples with amplitude weights of [0.25, -0.5, 1, -0.5, 0.25]) at the optical wavelengths of 1550, 1555, and 1560 nm.

2.5 Parallel 5G signal transmission

Beyond radiofrequency signal processing, we have demonstrated as well parallel 5G signal distribution along the seven 5-km fiber cores. With the aim of evaluating the possible effect of intercore crosstalk, we transmitted both 64/256-quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) signals (26-GHz central frequency, bandwidth up to 400MHz) generated by a vector signal generator R&S SMW200A. As a representative case (256QAM modulation, 200-MHz bandwidth), Fig. 3 (e) shows the constellation for the signal after transmission along core 1, while Fig. 3 (f) gathers the error vector magnitude (EVM) measured for all seven cores by an R&S FSW43 analyzer, where we can see that most cores (with exception of core 2) remain below the threshold for 256-QAM (4.5%).

Figure 3. Experimentally demonstrated microwave signal processing built upon a dispersion-diversity 7-core fiber: (a) microwave signal filtering, (b) radio beam-steering in a phased-array antenna, (c) frequency measurement, (d) arbitrary waveform generation, and (e,f) parallel 5G 256-QAM (26-GHz frequency, 200-MHz bandwidth) signal transmission showing (e) measured constellation for core 1 and (f) EVM (%) for every core .

Sampled true-time delay line operation can also be enabled by the different modes of a FMF, providing as an additional advantage a simpler and more cost-effective fabrication procedure compared to MCFs. Special attention must be paid to minimize intermodal crosstalk and modal noise [9]. As a first step, we experimentally demonstrated in the past a TTDL based on a commercial FMF with inscription of fiber Bragg gratings that fails to provide tunability [10]. Then, we theoretically proposed a new ring-core FMF that enables tunable operation but still requires the inscription of long-period gratings [11].

To overcome these limitations, we have developed a double-clad step-index few-mode fiber (refractive index profile shown in Fig. 4 (a)) [12], where the modes LP_{01} , LP_{11} , LP_{21} , LP_{31} , and LP_{41} (each one in a different group of modes) meet the necessary conditions to function as a continuously tunable TTDL. Specifically, the differential group delays (DGDs) between adjacent modes are identical at a particular wavelength and increase linearly with the optical wavelength. The fiber was produced by YOFC, with a silica core, and inner and outer claddings with radii of 9.1, 13, and 62.5 μm , respectively. The GeO_2 doping concentrations for the core, inner, and outer claddings are 7.79 mol%, 5.93 mol%, and 0.22 mol%, respectively. Fig. 4 (b) displays the DGD measurements of the modes in comparison to LP_{01} , which confirms the expected time delay tunability since $\Delta\tau$ increases linearly with the optical wavelength. The differential chromatic dispersion ΔD between adjacent modes was determined by calculating the derivative of the DGD values, obtaining relatively consistent steps of $\Delta D = 1.7$ ps/nm/km.

We have demonstrated a variety of microwave signal filters with this FMF. For instance, Fig. 4 (c) illustrates the normalized frequency response of a 5-tap filter using the 5 LP modes selected, i.e., operating in the space-diversity regime, for three different wavelengths. By sweeping the laser from 1530 to 1565 nm, we tuned $\Delta\tau$ continuously from 46.3 to 105.6 ps, therefore varying the filter's FSR from 21.6 down to 9.5 GHz. Successful tunable microwave filters were also implemented by exploiting the wavelength diversity.

Figure 4. Dispersion-diversity FMF: (a) Refractive index profile at 633 nm (the mode profiles of the 5 spatial modes selected for tunable TTDL operation are also shown), (b) Measured spectral differential group delays between LP_{01} mode and the rest, (c) Measured microwave signal filtering responses for space diversity.

We have successfully demonstrated a variety of tunable microwave signal processing applications built upon different dispersion-diversity SDM optical fibers. Both the heterogeneous 7-core fiber and the double-cladding few-mode fiber provide “by themselves” parallel dispersion-diversity signal processing along with network distribution, as each core/mode has been designed to provide the necessary chromatic dispersion for tunable operation. Within the particular context of radio-over-fiber architectures for radar and wireless communication systems, dispersion-diversity SDM optical fibers provides advantages in terms of compactness, versatility, and flexibility while also decreasing power consumption.

In addition to microwave photonics, our approach can apply as well to a wide range of ICT scenarios, including satellite communications, distributed antenna systems, fiber optic sensing, high-performance computing, optical coherence tomography and medical imaging, as well as electronic and radiofrequency measurement instrumentation.

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